

ORGANIZING ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND SOME ASPECTS OF
THEIR TRANSFER

Xolmatova Makhliyo Iskandar qizi

Teacher of the Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

Abstract: In the article higher in education mobile o ' yins organize and some aspects of their implementation are covered in detail.

Key words: Higher education, physical education, active game, activity, emotion, physical exercise, health improvement, national value, physical education.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ АКТИВНЫХ ИГР В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ И НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИХ ПОВЕДЕНИЯ

Холматова Махлиё Искандар қизи

Преподаватель Деновского института предпринимательства и педагогики

Аннотация: Организация подвижных игр в высшей школе в статье подробно освещены некоторые аспекты их реализации.

Ключевые слова: Высшее образование, физическое воспитание, активная игра, деятельность, эмоция, физические упражнения, оздоровление, национальная ценность, физическое воспитание.

Introduction. The teacher's mastery of the method of leading the game process is the main condition for successful games. Selection and planning of action games is carried out according to the program. This takes into account the working conditions of each age group, such as the general level of physical and mental development of children, the development of motor skills, the health status of each child, its own characteristics, the season, daily routine, and the arrangement of the house. place, as well as the specific characteristics of children's interests. Action games are gradually becoming more complicated in accordance with the requirements of the program, they are changed taking into account the growth of children's minds, the movement experience they have gained, and the need to prepare them for school.

In terms of content and rules, are organized. In these games, all children perform the same role or task with the direct participation of the teacher (all children are birds, the teacher is the mother bird...).

3-year-old children are gradually taught to play roles independently (all children are birds, one or two children are cars).

The middle group, the simplest competitive games can be played both individually and as a team.

Games for children in a large group are complicated according to their content, rules, number of roles, introduction of submission to team competition.

Children of the school preparatory group play some complex movement games, as well as team games consisting of team competitions, game relays, sports games. All this helps to develop agility, quickness, endurance, improve movement skills, and educate moral and willful qualities.

Children to a new game. Explaining its content and rules requires thorough preparation from the teacher. It is possible to clarify children's knowledge on the basis of conversations that take place in advance of the content of some games. Their imagination determines, the attitude towards the game images is formed, the basic imagination grows.

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The Games Can Vary Depending On Their Type, But The Activity Is Always Emotionally interesting, prepares children for fun play activities, makes them want to start playing faster, and makes them enthusiastic about the game tasks. should be motivated to perform with.

The game without content should be short, clear and expressive. The teacher explains the sequence of game actions, shows the location of children and game attributes (targeting objects in small and medium groups, and non-targeting in large groups) using spatial expressions and rules clarifies. After that, the teacher asks the children some questions.

The game are understandable to children, the game will be fun and organized.

Games with elements of competition, the educator explains the rules, methods of the game, conditions of the competition, and encourages children to try and do the tasks well, giving confidence in doing them well. Taking into account the physical maturity and individual characteristics of the children, the educator unites equal groups - teams, competing forces; pairs insecure, shy children with bold, active children in order to activate them.

Sometimes team captains, the referee and his assistants can be chosen to give the game a sporting appearance.

Meaningful games. The teacher's task is to create a visual picture of the game situation before the children's eyes , to vividly describe the game images, to influence the children's imagination and feelings, and to activate their creative initiative. For this, small groups can use toys and stories.

Middle groups, it is enough to limit yourself to offering a familiar game and mentioning its rules.

In large groups, it is advisable to invite the children themselves to remember the content of the game . One of them describes the course of game actions, the other lists the rules . Later, the children themselves start to organize the game without the help of the teacher.

Distribution of roles in the game. The educator follows pedagogical tasks (encouraging the newcomer child or, on the contrary, proving how important it is to be a hero in the case of an active child, or rejecting the request of a confident child and giving this role to a shy child who is afraid handover) appoints a leader or takes the role of a leader or ordinary participant by entering the game himself, making the children happy.

Also, the presenter can refer the children to him and ask them to explain why they assigned this role to this child.

The role of leader in a small group is performed by the teacher himself . During the game, the educator monitors children's actions and interactions, compliance with the rules, gives brief instructions, manages children's emotional states. He will talk about the violation of the rule by some children before restarting the game.

The game. The active game is completed with a general walk, which reduces the physical load. Walking can also be replaced with low-motion play of equal importance .

It is over, the child's slow transition from fast movement to rest will have an unpleasant effect on the heart and the whole body. When evaluating the game , the educator emphasizes its positive aspects, names the children who successfully fulfilled their roles, showed courage, endurance, mutual support, and complains about the violation of the rules and the children's actions related to this. shows.

In large groups, the educator prepares children to independently organize active games, while monitoring the progress of the games and especially the fulfillment of the rules, as well as

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the relationships between the children . He gives children tasks such as inventing variants of mobile games by changing their content, rules, game actions, and then finding a new game of their own .

In order to educate the children of the large group of independence and organizational skills, the educator offers them to organize a game with the children of the small group. The game is played under the supervision of a small group educator.

Active games are important in the comprehensive education of children. No matter how the game activity is expressed, it pleases the child and evokes positive feelings in them . Active games expand the child's worldview, are a unique tool for learning about the environment.

of action games determine the course of the game, guide children's movement activities, mutual relations, and help to educate moral and willful qualities.

It is important for every child to understand the rules of the game and to be guided by adults. Moral qualities such as honesty, justice, friendship, bravery, self-control, determination are brought up in children through games .

Game activities, favorable conditions are created for the development of attention, perception, thinking, understanding and targeting, games help to develop creative imagination, memory, ingenuity, thinking activity. Thus, active games help the child's mental development.

The game activity, the child practically assimilates the reality of space and objects, and at the same time, he himself greatly improves the mechanism of space perception.

Direction of movement by the child and the execution of the movement in the direction strictly defined by the rules of the game, on the one hand, the immediate assessment of the game situation (directly perceived) and visual-motor reaction (game actions) , on the other hand, requires understanding and imagining their actions in a space-game environment.

Action games form a simple time frame in children. They are expressed in the following: in understanding the sequence of game actions, first, then, next, before, all at the same time, it is seen in the rapid performance of game tasks according to the signal, within the time limit set for children. In these games, children practice aiming in space, consistency of actions and following them over time.

The games, the entire game situation, its rules, the movement of the characters, showing the location of the children, game attributes and directions of movement using spatial expressions, evaluating the played game serves the mental development of children.

Action games facilitate the development of creativity in older children. In this case, children can invent small games based on the content of the stories they have heard. Movement games are aesthetic activities based on their content and form . The variety of game actions is expressed in the fact that children perform them with clear agility and unique expression. The use of music in action games has great aesthetic value.

Action games, one should not forget the beauty and culture of actions: it is necessary to pay attention to children whose actions are somewhat expressive, to encourage those who are able to give expressive and successful images.

It is a complex activity consisting of various emotional movements. This activity is performed on the basis of established rules in conditions and situations that change suddenly . Action games differ in the features of organizing and managing the activities of the participants.

During the game, physical qualities such as movement and quickness, agility (distraction, avoiding "traps") are demonstrated in situations that suddenly change.

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During the game, children's activities are organized on the basis of a figurative plot or game tasks, and this creates positive feelings for the child to perform physical exercises with enthusiasm and for a long time. This, in turn, strengthens their effect on the body, helps to develop endurance.

Games, especially in work with children of preschool age, gives good results.

Action games are an important complex educational process. Children's movement activity, which is the basis of this process, has a positive effect on physical development, the formation of movement skills and physical qualities, and strengthening of health by increasing the functional activity of the body and enhancing feelings of emotional joy. Action games as one of the main means and methods of physical education help to effectively solve the tasks listed above.

Active games is inextricably linked with the positive emotions that arise during children's game activities and have a positive effect on the child's psyche. Emotional upliftment awakens children's desire to achieve a goal common to all, and it is expressed in a clear understanding of tasks, mutual compatibility of actions, accurate targeting in space and game conditions, and accelerated execution of tasks. Due to children's strong desire to achieve the goal and enjoyable pursuit, the role of willpower, which helps to overcome various obstacles, increases.

Movement games serve as a method of improving movement skills acquired by children and training physical qualities. During the game, the child focuses on achieving the goal, not on the method of performing the action. He acts according to the conditions of the game, showing agility and thus improving the movements. Therefore, for example, the game "Wolf in the ravine" is given after children learn to run and long jump.

As a movement activity, movement play has certain special features: it requires the child to quickly respond to signals and sudden changes in the game. Different situations and actions that occur in the game require changes in the level of muscle tension. For example, in the game "Trap", each child should carefully follow the leader's actions: when the leader approaches him, he quickly runs away in the opposite direction; when he feels safe, he moves slowly and stops; accelerates again when the starter approaches.

Almost every action game has actions and cues for children's movements. Such active movement activities train the child's nervous system, improving and balancing the processes of excitation and inhibition, as well as observation, ingenuity, the ability to aim in a changing environment, find a way out of a difficult situation, quickly educates decision-making and its implementation, bravery, initiative, choosing an independent way to achieve the goal.

The origin of action games goes back to ancient folk pedagogy. Children of the first age are brought up in families with the help of toys and fun games related to the child's initial movements. In the lives of children older than that, folk games with colorful action content (including game beginnings that frame children, khyrgyi, counting) have a great place. All of these still retain their artistic appeal, educational value and constitute valuable game folklore.

Selection and planning of action games is carried out according to the program. It takes into account the working conditions of each age group, such as the general level of physical and mental development of children, the development of movement skills, the health status of each child, its own characteristics, the season, daily routine, and the arrangement of the house. place, as well as the specific characteristics of children's interests. Action games are gradually becoming more complicated in accordance with the requirements of the program, they are changed taking into account the growth of children's minds, the movement experience they have gained, and the need to prepare them for school.

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Games for children in a large group are complicated according to their content, rules, number of roles, introduction of submission to team competition.

It was concluded from this study that the children of the preparatory group at the school play some complex movement games , as well as team games consisting of team competitions, game relay, and sports games. All this helps to develop agility, quickness, endurance, improve movement skills, and educate moral and willful qualities .

Children to a new game . Explanation of its content and rules requires thorough preparation from the educator. It is possible to clarify children's knowledge on the basis of conversations that take place in advance of the content of some games . Their imagination determines, the attitude towards the game images is formed, the basic imagination grows.

References:

1. TS Usmonkho' jaev "Action games" Study guide T.: Teacher 1992
Methodology of organizing and holding sports holidays" Textbook T.: 2008
3. Khojayev P, Rakhimkulov KD, Nigmanov BB "Action games and their teaching methodology" Cholpon publishing house T.: 2010.
4. R.I.Azizova " Methodology of teaching sports and action games" Manual T.: 2010
5. K. D. Rakhimkulov "National Movement Games" Study guide T.: 2012
6. Zhukov M.N. - M.: Podvizhnye igry: Ucheb. for stud. ped. Vuzov. Izdatelsky center "Academy" 2000. - 160 p.
7. Khojaev F, Murodov M, Mirsolikhov.S. "People's National Games Part 1. Toshken - 2001.